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Mentorship Model “Educator-Student-Pupil” in the System of Continuing Education of Kazan Federal University

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Abstract

The relevance of this study is based on the acute demand for young teachers who are able to quickly respond to changes in the educational situation and to new conditions of professional activity. The introduction of a teacher's professional standard entails changes in training and retraining in higher education. At the same time, the Professional Standard increases a teacher's responsibility for the results of his/her work, and impose the requirements for his/her qualifications and professional competencies.

The problem of the study is the fact that the Professional Standard increases demands on the teacher and it is aimed at achieving the three most important areas of the educational results: education, training and development of children. In this regard, there is a need of creating a model of mentoring in the Kazan Federal University “teacher-student-student”, which will be focused on the formation and development of professional competencies of teachers and students of the university. Specifically, it will be concentrated on future elementary school teachers and on students who conduct educational and developmental activities with children of primary school age in the children's theater Kazan who "Rainbow" Federal University. The three-module model of mentoring "teacher-student-student" is aimed at implementing the requirements of the Federal state educational standards of higher and primary education, the Professional standard of the teacher, the development of creative and acting skills of students of grades 1-4.

The purpose of the study is to develop a mentorship model "educator-student-pupil" in the children's theater of Kazan Federal University. Methods of this study are the following: theoretical (theoretical analysis of pedagogical, psychological, scientific and methodical literature on the topic of research), empirical (analysis, comparison, synthesis, content selection, observation, questioning), pedagogical experiment (establishing, forming and control stages of the experiment), expert assessment method, statistical processing of quantitative research results.

In the course of our research, it was revealed that the teacher-student-student mentoring model in the system of continuous education at Kazan Federal University has three substantive blocks: the content of the teacher's teaching activities and the requirements for the teacher; the content of pedagogical activity and requirements for the student; the content of educational activities of younger schoolchildren in the children's theater and the requirements for students. Requirements for teachers and students of the university: high professional competence; socio-economic competence; communicative competence; high level of professional and general culture. Primary schoolchildren form competencies according to their creative and acting abilities: the basics of theatrical culture; speech culture; emotional and imaginative development; musical development; basics of graphic design activities; foundations of collective creative activity.

We have proved that the mentoring model "teacher-student-pupil" had an impact on all participants of the educational process: on teachers, on students, on pupils. In the course of theatrical activity, there were high-quality changes in the following: professional formation and development of students, a formation of professional competences of future teachers of the elementary school, creative and actor's development of younger school students; education of personal, social and family culture of children. The organization of individual mentoring, psychology and pedagogical scaffolding of the child actor, use of interactive games and technologies, subject role-playing games, use of receptions of staging, dramatization, staging, improvisation.

The practical significance of this article is determined by the possibility of using its results in the future educational process in universities, primary schools, and in the management of educational institutions.

Keywords: mentorship model, student, professor, pupil, formation, professional standard, development, professional competence, children's theater, primary school.

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Introduction

1. The relevance of the problem

One of the actual problems of preparing the future teacher today is the reluctance of graduates of pedagogical universities to work at schools, lack of motivation to master the teaching profession, the gap between theoretical knowledge and their practical application. An effective means of solving these problems is mentoring as a model of the developing interaction of the future teacher with the teacher-teacher, aimed at the transfer of pedagogical experience.

In a modern university, a teacher is assigned to the role of not a “knowledge translator”, but a mentor, a tutor, an assistant who can set the vector of students' professional, creative, and personal development. The main purpose of practical training in a modern university is to create conditions for the future specialist to master the skill of solving professional problems both in situations of real activity' simulations and through an actual experience of professional activity. According to the Federal State Educational Standards of Higher Education, a teacher should not only perfectly master the subject of teaching, but also be fully developed and work with his/her students simultaneously in three main areas: education, upbringing of children, and assistance in their development.

Today, the main idea of “life-long learning” is the idea of continuing education of a person. The system of continuous pedagogical education requires the creation of the necessary scientific, pedagogical and methodological conditions for the creation and implementation of a mentoring model in the children's theater of the KFU "Raduga" "teacher-student-student" in the continuing education system of the Kazan Federal University. This model responds to the challenges of modern higher and secondary general education and is the real embodiment of the KFU “Teacher of the 21st Century” Project. The project of the Kazan Federal University “Teacher of the 21st Century” is aimed to train teachers of the new generation who work effectively in the conditions of digitalization of the economy and society, ethnic and cultural diversity. This project solves the problems of modern higher pedagogical education: the implementation of innovative practices in the teaching and professional development of teachers; training of leaders who are ready for change and capable of shaping and implementing an innovative vision of the educational process for a successful future of new generations of students.

The innovative model of mentoring in the KFU "teacher-student-student" includes three modules: 1) teacher; 2) a student; 3) a student - and it is based on the pedagogical interaction and the pedagogy of cooperation.

This model assumes that teachers communicate with each other, communicate with students, students communicate with children-theater actors, children interact with a teacher during classes, and therefore, there is pedagogical cooperation between teachers and students of the university, teachers and younger school children, between students and primary school students.

Mentoring is a process of purposeful formation of a personality, its intellect, physical strength, spirituality, and the preparation for life, and to actively participate in the work activity. Mentoring is a two-way process: on the one hand, the activity of the mentor, on the other hand - the activity of the student. This process is reciprocal in nature and it is one of the varieties of pedagogical interaction.

According to scientists, pedagogical interaction is a systematic, continuous implementation of communicative actions of the teacher, with the aim of provoking a reaction from the learner, and the evoked reaction, in turn, causes the

reaction of the influencer. This is a specific form of communication, established in the course of a holistic educational process.

However, at the moment, in the pedagogical theory, the system of developing interaction between a teacher-mentor and a student, remain undeveloped. Particularly, the transformation of forms, content and models of translation of pedagogical experience into a system of developing interaction.

2. State of elaboration of the problem

The problem of interaction has been studied by scientists such as Barabanova (2008), Diachenko (1991), Zimniaia (2004), Kan-Kalik (1987), Orlov (2001), and Radionova (1989).

An activity based on "live communication" as a way of information exchange and the mutual influence on each other, and also, aimed at significant changes of states, behaviour and personal-semantic formations of partners was considered by Ananyev (1977), Gorshkova (2009), Kagan (1988), Kan-Kalik (1987), Orlov (2001), Petrovskii (1989), Radionova (1989), and Zaripova (as cited in Butenko & Butenko, 2016). Moreover, Butenko & Butenko (2016) considers the features of mentorship activity' construction.

Thereby, pedagogical interaction involves pedagogical and psychological knowledge about childish, adolescent and youthful age, specific goals, content and technology in contexts of an educational institution.

Despite the sufficient amount of studies on the problem of mentorship, pedagogical interaction of teachers and pupils, the question of conditions, principles, content and forms of interaction, monitoring and analysis of in the system "professor-student-pupil", which would allow to systematically assess the effectiveness of mentorship, remains unexplored.

3. Theoretical and practical contribution of the article

- The model of pedagogical interaction and mentoring "teacher-student-student" in the system of continuous education of the Kazan Federal University, aimed at training, educating and developing students "student-student" and the formation of professional competencies of students, professional development of teachers has been developed.

- The mentoring model in the children's theater of the Kazan Federal University suggests using the principles of the pedagogy of cooperation.

- It has been substantiated that students in grades 1–4 develop creative and acting abilities of children in 6 blocks: the basics of theatrical culture; speech culture; emotional and imaginative development; musical development; basics of graphic design activities; foundations of collective creative activity.

- It has been proved that the mentor model "teacher-student-student" involves the organization of individual mentoring, psychological and pedagogical support of the child-actor, the use of interactive games and technologies, role-playing games, the use of dramatization, dramatization, theatrical, and improvisation techniques.

The purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to develop a mentorship model "professor-student-pupil" in the children's theater of Kazan Federal University.

Objectives of the study:

1. To create the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the three-module mentorship model "professor-student-pupil" in the children's theater of KFU;

2. To prove the effectiveness of pedagogical interaction in the mentorship model «professor-student-pupil»;

3. To develop guidelines for the implementation of this model at pedagogical universities in Russia and foreign countries.

Literature review

1. Russian literature review

Ananyev (1997) explores interrelations between the macroenvironment, the microenvironment and the individual. This complexity of interrelationships was the regulator of the social development of the individual. Roles, behavior motivation, value orientations, the structure and dynamics of relationships are all characteristics of a person (Ananyev, 1977).

Barabanova (2008) considered the pupil as a subject of educational changes, an accomplice of the pedagogical process, a creative personality, but not as an object of external influences and impacts. We will list different approaches to the organization of pedagogical interaction such as activity-based, personality-oriented, acmeological, axiological and systemic approaches. The position of the teacher in the implementation of subject-subject interaction involves 1. The manifestation of the value attitude to the personality of the pupil. 2. Implementation of new pedagogical roles of the teacher (Barabanova, 2008).

Gorshkova (2009) develops the concept of dialogue in education aimed at reforming the traditional system of school and university education. The scientist revealed the ontology of dialogue as a form of methodological intention and a universal way of designing educational space as a space of human existence (Gorshkova, 2009).

Dyachenko (1991) used the idea of mutual learning not highlighting the existing level of knowledge and abilities but including all children in a feasible dialogue-communication using the form of dynamic (changing) couples in which the child acts either as a student or as a teacher. According to Dyachenko (1991), the organizational structure of group learning methods can be combined, in particular, it can contain various forms: group (when one teaches many), pair, individual. And yet, group communication is dominant.

Zimniaia (2004) studies pedagogical communication based on the activity-based approach. Pedagogical communication is a form of educational interaction, cooperation between teachers and pupils. According to her, pedagogical communication is an axial-retinal, personal and socially-oriented interaction. Additionally, pedagogical communication includes communicative, perceptive and interactive functions, using the entire set of verbal, graphic, symbolic and kinetic aspects (Zimniaia, 2004).

Kagan (1998) revealed the features of communication, considering interpersonal relationships, relationships of social groups, communication of cultures, self-communication based on the principles of the systematic approach and involving extensive material from social practice, the history of science, literature and art.

Kan-Kalik (1987) considered typical difficulties arising in communication between the teacher and the class, revealed the secrets of pedagogical communication, issues of education and training related to the contact of teachers and children. The author interprets the process of pedagogical communication and oneself from the point of view of the teacher and the student (Kan-Kalik, 1987).

Orlov (1995) formulated the principles of the organization of pedagogical interaction: dialogization, problematization, personalization, individualization.

Petrovskii (1989) studied the problem of personality formation in which the scientist recognised three phases of development: adaptation, individualization, integration. A child of the primary school age also naturally goes through three phases of its formation of personality. However, it is not so much the educational activity as the attitude of adults to his educational activities, academic performance, discipline and diligence act as a factor in the development of the personality of the younger student. The third phase of the period of the primary school age does not mean the integration of the child in the system of "pupils — pupils" but in the system of "pupils — teacher", "pupils — parents" (Petrovskii, 1989).

Radionova (1989) studies the position of the teacher in the process of interaction with students. There are several types of teachers in her classification of mentorship: teacher-facilitator, teacher-consultant, teacher-moderator, teacher-tutor and teacher-coach.

Zaripova (as cited in Butenko & Butenko, 2016) suggested evaluating the mentorship activity of the teacher through three stages. The first stage is the motivation of students to work independently and the aid of a mentor to determine specific goals which the student would like to implement in the process of an educational activity. The second stage is the formation of skills, abilities and knowledge necessary for the student to independently practice the educational process. On the third stage, students acquire the skill of reflection and evaluation of their own practice. (Butenko, 2016).

2. International literature review

The international community of researchers studies the problem of mentorship as a multidimensional process that affects the development of professional competencies of the mentor, a young teacher or student.

A polish scientist Bitinas (1996) considering the educational process emphasized the interaction of the teacher and students. According to the researcher, it is necessary to take into account the following: age of pupils in a class; the degree of

formation of children's collective features of the relationship of the class teacher and pupils; the degree of trust of children to each other and to adults (Bitinas, 1996).

Mackie (2018) presents a Scottish perspective on the international mentorship model of teachers and students and provides a new understanding of mentorship by considering the role of mentees as well as a mentor.

Gardiner & Weisling (2018) studied the problem and difficulties of developing the practice of mentorship and they focused on the vocational training and practice of young mentors. The scientists concluded that mentors tried to handle numerous complex relationships with administrators, teachers, and students, and perceived their mentorship work as effective professional development. However, the young mentors noted that it was the most difficult to apply knowledge in practice (Gardiner & Weisling, 2018).

English researcher Lofthouse (2018) defined mentorship as a dynamical system of transformation of primary teacher education. Mentorship can be also reinterpreted as the dynamical system within a framework of the practice-based development model for individual professional training and institutional growth.

A group of researchers Busse, Campbell, & Kipping (2018) has developed a classification of mentorship programs for young people in secondary schools in the United Kingdom. The authors have developed the mentorship programs in three categories: mentor type (a senior pupil, school staff, an adult volunteer), a program setting (school, community, online), and a program goal. The findings suggest that, although mentorship programmes are considerably diverse, it is possible to group them into two mentorship programmes. The first is "for personality and development" and the second is "for learning and employment" and to draw the distinctions between 12 common mentorship models (Busse, Campbell & Kipping, 2018).

Scientists from Qatar University Abu-Tineh & Sadiq (2018) supposed that the most effective model of professional development is the mentor model named "a skilled teacher is a young teacher." School teachers in Qatar adopt and use this mentorship model based on professional support from an experienced teacher towards a newly hired teacher (Abu-Tineh & Sadiq, 2018).

Ehri & Flugman (2018) studied the results of a one-year mentorship program aimed at improving the knowledge and effectiveness of teachers in the field of teaching phonetics, and also the degree of improvement of pupils' performance in reading and spelling. The mentors worked with kindergarten teachers and 1st, 2nd and 3rd grade pupils twice a week for 30 weeks throughout the year. Each visit included a 45-minute preparation period and 45-minute modeling and class feedback. Mentors taught teachers how to teach the system of phonetics to their pupils. Monthly mentor ratings showed that teachers improved their skills of teaching phonetic, besides many of them achieved the highest grades by the end of the academic year (Ehri & Flugman, 2018).

Mukeredzi (2018) said about the experience of mentorship describing the students and the mentors enrolled to the bachelor's program. The scientist recommends systematically organize the mentorship practices and support for novice teachers through a comprehensive continuing training.

Betlem, Clary, & Jones (2018) explore the problem of teacher mentorship and how to implement professional development through a partnership between schools and universities. Australian scholars describe the development and implementation of a context-based professional development model using collaborative research aimed at developing the mentoring ability of teachers and developing a collaborative research culture. Scientists suggested a formal partnership between higher education institutions, schools and education systems providing the teacher education and professional development, particularly for mentors, especially in rural schools (Betlem, Clary & Jones, 2018).

Methodology

1. Theoretical and empirical methods.

To test the hypothesis, a set of various methods complementary to each other was used: theoretical - analysis of the works of teachers and psychologists on the research problem; analysis of methodological and educational literature; theoretical analysis of the main dimensions of the used methodology; theoretical confirmation of the model of pedagogical interaction and mentorship "teacher-student-student" in the system of continuous education of the Kazan Federal University;

Empirical methods included observation, stating and forming pedagogical experiment, questioning, testing, conversations, analysis of the results of experimental work.

2. Study Base

The research was carried out in the Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan (Volga region) Federal University and secondary schools № 5, 9, 16 of the Republic of Tatarstan. 62 students, 12 teachers-mentors, 31 pupils of the primary school took part in experimental work. The experiment was conducted in 2017-2018 and in 2018-2019 academic years.

The study was conducted in three stages. At the first stage, experiments were conducted on the basis of the above-mentioned secondary schools of the Republic of Tatarstan. The process of teaching primary school pupils and the mentorship forms were observed. Then, questioning and interviews with primary school students and teachers were conducted. Furthermore, the level of development of creative and acting abilities of children and the formation of professional competencies of students and teachers were detected. Finally, the study topic was tested at the initial stage of the experiment.

At the second stage, the theoretical concept of the study was refined and corrected, a training experiment was conducted in primary schools of the Republic of Tatarstan: MBOU Gymnasium No. 5 with the ethnocultural Tatar component, Lyceum No. 9 named after A. Sushchenko, MBOU Gymnasium No. 16 with the Tatar language of instruction of the Zelenodolsk municipal district of the Republic of Tatarstan. The experiment involved 31 people. They were the 1-4 grades pupils of the primary school.

At the third stage, the analysis, synthesis and systematization of the data obtained, the design of the study; The approbation of the research topic was carried out in publications and speeches of the author at scientific conferences.

3. Evaluation criteria

Evaluation of the level of development of creative and acting abilities of children, the formation of professional competencies of students and professors was carried out according to the developed criteria: low level – from 25 to 50 points; average level – from 51 to 75 points; high level – from 76 to 100 points. The effectiveness of the mentorship model was determinate using the technique by Zaripova (as cited in Butenko & Butenko, 2016) was used, consisting of three stages of mentorship activity.

Findings

1. Progress and description of the establishing stage of the experiment.

At the establishing stage of the experiment, a survey was conducted with pupils of grades 1–4 to assess the development of theatrical and creative culture of primary school pupils (children's theater actors) in six blocks: the fundamentals of theatrical culture; speech culture; emotional and imaginative development; musical development; fundamentals of graphic design activities; basics of collective creative activity. According to the first block, “Fundamentals of Theater Culture”, the following skills were tested: a manifestation of sustained interest in theatrical art and theatrical activity; knowledge of the rules of behaviour in the theater; knowledge of various types of theater and their differences; characteristics of theatrical professions. In the second block, “Speech Culture”, the following skills were tested such as understanding of the main idea of a literary work; giving detailed verbal characteristics of the main and minor characters; creative interpretation of plot units based on a literary work.

In the third block, “Emotional-figurative development,” skills were tested: He creatively applies knowledge of various emotional states and characters in performances and uses various means of the educator.

In the fourth block, Musical Development, the following skills were tested: improvisation to the music of different nature, the creation of expressive images, selection of the musical characters and music to parts of the plot, independent use of musical accompaniment on the media, performance a song or dance in the play.

According to the fifth block, “Fundamentals of graphic design activities”, the following skills were checked: the ability to independently create sketches for the main actions of the performance, sketches of scenery and characters, and imagination in the process of creation scenery and characters for performances of various types of theater. In the sixth block, “Basics of Collective Creative Activity,” the following skills were tested: the manifestation of the initiative with partners and creative activity at all stages of the performance.

of the pupils		qualities and professional competences)	the student-teacher of primary school	of the pupils	with children	(personal qualities and professional competences	of the student-teacher of primary school
6 9,2%	66,5 %	65,3 %	68,5%	6 0%	62, 5%	6 1%	63%

Evaluation of formation of students-bachelors' professional competences and young teachers of "Lyceum №9" revealed the average level of formation of professional competences (from 60% to 63% - in the control group; from 65.3% to 69.2% -in the experimental group).

2. Progress and description of the forming stage of the experiment

During 2017-2019 school years, we used the mentoring model “teacher - student-student” in the children's theater of the Kazan Federal University. This model of mentoring includes three modules: 1) a teacher as a subject of the educational process, interacting with students in grades 1–4; 2) a student as a subject of the educational process, interacting with the teacher, other students and students of grades 1-4; 3) an elementary school student as a subject of the educational process, interacting with a teacher, students and other students in a children's theater.

The pedagogue of the children's theater of the Kazan Federal University served as a mentor for students and pupils. Pedagogy's responsibilities included directing the pedagogical and creative activities of students and pupils, psychological and pedagogical support for pupils in grades 1–4, teaching acting and stage skills of children and students and teaching communication skills. The teacher was in the center of pedagogical interaction in the mentoring model “teacher - student-student” and as a result, pedagogical and creative activity in the children's theater depended on it.

According to the Professional Standard of the teacher, the teacher should not only perfectly master the subject of teaching, but also be fully developed and work with his/her students simultaneously in three main areas: education, parenting, and assistance in their development. A university student was an individual mentor of a particular child. His/her responsibilities included psychological and pedagogical support for a child of primary school age, tutoring assistance in training sessions and rehearsals for performances in children's theater, pedagogical interaction with children during the “immersion” role, learning to sing and dance, expressive reading, teaching stage speech, the basics of the scenic movement.

In the course of the formative experiment, the teacher instructed the students to perform the following tasks, focused on teaching acting skills and pedagogical interaction with children:

1. To conduct a rehearsal of the performance;
2. To conduct training for team agreement;
3. To conduct educational and educational games;
4. To Conduct physical fasting;
5. To conduct musical-dynamic exercises;
6. Conduct a check of the text role played by children;
7. Show a sample of an expressive reading of an artwork;
8. Show a sample of stage speech and stage movement performed by the role;
9. Compose a slide presentation for the performance.
10. Make music for the play.

Pupils of grades 1-4 - actors of a children's theater - were engaged in an additional program of developmental education “Creative and acting development of school children”. Themes of the children's theater in the 2017-2018: 1. Stage speech and stage movement. 2. Analysis of artwork. 3. Work on the play “The Cat's House” by S. Ya. Marshak. 4. Work on the New Year fairy tale “Journey to the XXX Century.” 5. Work on the production of the play based on the novel by Leo Tolstoy “Childhood”. 6. Theatre literature Victory Day musical performance “We are the patriots of our Fatherland”.

The abovementioned content of the children's theater led to the development of the creative and acting abilities of primary school children and the formulation of the following professional competencies of mentor students: 1. Scenic speech. 2. Scenic movement and dance. 3. Features of a puppet theater. 4. Individual work of the actor with a puppet. 5. A puppet theater and playing with a partner in a puppet theater. 6. Evaluating fables and fairy tales in a puppet theater. 7. Theatrical folklore festival "Our Fun Fair" (in Russian, Tatar, English) .8. Features of the finger theater. 9. The Finger Theater. Staging etudes in the finger theater.10. The history of the creation of the Imperial Kazan University. 11. Rehearsal and premiere of the play "Vivat, KFU!" dedicated to the 215th anniversary of Kazan Federal University.

The specificity of the mentoring model "teacher-student-student" is that the training and rehearsal classes for children of primary school age were conducted by mentor students. This is an individual mentoring, because each child has a mentor. Thus, the child-actor in children's theater receives pedagogical assistance from both the teacher and the student tutor.

3. Progress and description of the control stage of the experiment

At the control stage of the experiment, a questionnaire consisted of six blocks was conducted with 1-4 grades pupils that determined the level of development of creative and acting abilities of primary school pupils.

Table 5. Formation and development of creative and acting abilities of children of primary school age (Experimental group)

The basics of theatrical culture	Speech culture	Emotional and figurative development	Musical development	The basics of graphic design activity	The basics of collective creative activity
91%	88%	87%	86%	85%	92%

Table 6. Formation and development of creative and acting abilities of children of primary school age (Control group)

The basics of theatrical culture	Speech culture	Emotional and figurative development	Musical development	The basics of graphic design activity	The basics of collective creative activity
66%	67%	64%	68%	69%	68%

Analysis of children's skills on the first block "Bases of Theatrical Culture" showed that the experimental group shows a steady interest in theater and theatrical activity; recognize the rules of conduct in theater; know different types of theater and their distinctions, and can characterize theatrical professions. The level of development of pupils of this group – high-91% whereas pupils of control group are at the average level – 66%.

Analysis of children's skills on the second block "Speech Culture" showed that pupils of experimental group understand the main idea of the literary work; give detailed verbal characteristics of the main and minor characters; creatively interpret plot units on the basis of the literary work; are able to retell the work from different positions, using language and intonational and figurative means of expressiveness of the speech. The level of development of pupils of this group – high-88% whereas pupils of control group are at the average level – 67%.

Analysis of children's skills on the third block "Emotional and Figurative Development" demonstrated the high level of development of experimental group – 87% whereas pupils of control group are at the average level – 64%. The

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79,5%	82,7%	83,3%	85,5%	63,5%	67,5%	69%	68%

Table 8. Level of formation of teachers' professional competencies (according to the Professional standard of the teacher) (Experimental and control groups)

Analysis of formation of professional competencies showed a high level of formation of professional competencies in the experimental group (students of University) – from 79.5% to 85.5%; and the average level – in the control group (young teachers of the Lyceum) – from 63.5% to 69%.

Thus, the developing interaction of the mentorship model of "professor-student-pupil" occupies a central place in the process of professional development of the future teacher and it is the connecting link between the theoretical and methodological components of this process. The interaction "professor-student-pupil" reflect its characteristics: the type of relations between subjects of interaction (value relationships that contribute to the assimilation of professionally significant values), the style of communication (dialogic, based on cooperation), features the construction of joint activities (mutual enrichment of subjects through joint pedagogical activity), focus (on the formation of pedagogical abilities and professional pedagogical competence of the student).

Table 9. The level of determining the effectiveness of the mentorship model "professor-student-pupil" (Zaripova (as cited in Butenko & Butenko, 2016)) (Experimental group)

Motivation of students to pedagogical activity				Formation of skills, abilities, and knowledge base of students for independent work			Reflexive activity
Creating and supporting interest in self-study activities	Training the skills of independent educational process	Consideration of the expected results of self-study activities on specific examples	Regular participation and assistance of a mentor in the formation and development of students' skills	The creation of a sustainable stimulus to the mobilization of students' all internal reserves	Maximum immersion of students in the process of working with new information	Assistance and promotion in the formation of skills and the ability to generate new knowledge, conclusions	Acquiring the skill of assessment of the work accomplished and the mastery of reflective activities by students
89%	91%	92%	90%	93%	94%	92%	95%

Table 9. The level of determining the effectiveness of the mentorship model "professor-student-pupil" (Zaripova (as cited in Butenko & Butenko, 2016)) (Control group)

Motivation of students to pedagogical activity				Formation of skills, abilities, and knowledge base of students for independent work			Reflexive activity
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supporting interest in self-study activities	skills of independent educational process	the expected results of self-study activities on specific examples	participation and assistance of a mentor in the formation and development of students' skills	sustainable stimulus to the mobilization of students' all internal reserves	immersion of students in the process of working with new information	and promotion in the formation of skills and the ability to generate new knowledge, conclusions	of assessment of the work accomplished and the mastery of reflective activities by students
72 %	71 %	73 %	70 %	73 %	72 %	71 %	72%

Analysis of the effectiveness of the mentorship model "professor-student-pupil" showed that the organization and implementation of this model requires the following pedagogical actions of the mentor: motivation of students to pedagogical activity, the formation of skills, abilities, and knowledge base of students for independent work, reflexive activity. The experimental group showed a high level of motivation of students -90.6%; of formation of skills for independent work - 90.3%, of reflexive activity – 95%. The control group showed the average level of formation of the motivation of students- 72%, of skills and abilities for independent activity - 71,6%, of reflexive activity – 72%. In the process of professional activity of the teacher-mentor, it is assumed: saturation of the space of developing professional interaction with problematic pedagogical situations that require students to display professional activity and creativity; enrichment of positive experience of interaction (emotional, practical, and communicative) and establishing relations with students, colleagues. The process of transfer of pedagogical experience in the system of developing interaction "professor-student-pupil" organically integrated into the process of professional student training.

Discussions

The main forms to transfer pedagogical experience in our model of mentoring "teacher-student-pupil" are: the pedagogical workshops which are carried out for students by the teacher head of children's theater "Raduga"; interactive games; subject role-playing games, adaptations for a stage, dramatization, staging, improvisation; rehearsals of performances; creation of own scenario of a performance. The main experience is joint pedagogical activity of the teacher-mentor and student in which the student consistently performs roles of the assistant to the teacher, the assistant producer, the assistant to the screenwriter, the associate director of children's theater, the costumier, the decorator, the musical editor, the lighter, the master of drawing up the electronic presentation.

Thus, the main criteria of formation of professional competence of the student, future teacher criteria are following: 1) the ability to update pedagogical experience of the teacher-mentor, to take his core values and the ideas, to analyze the pedagogical methods applied by the teacher, receptions, means, technologies; 2) the ability to transfer the studied pedagogical experience to own professional activity, to integrate subjective experience with pedagogical experience of the teacher, and to own pedagogical values with the teacher's values); 3) the ability to apply the studied pedagogical experience to the analysis and the solution of pedagogical situations; 4) the ability to master students' pedagogical experience of the teacher-mentor, and the corresponding pedagogical abilities. Mentoring in the mentoring model "teacher-student-pupil" assumes realization by the teacher of new pedagogical functions (roles): teacher as interlocutor; the teacher as the person creating conditions for the doctrine; teacher as a researcher; teacher as a psychotherapist; teacher as an expert. Interaction of teachers and students

has a rich potential of self-development; influence on development on teaching and educational process, a system in which it is developed; improvement and enrichment of creative potential of its participants, humanization of their relations.

In the course of our research, we came to the conclusion that student learning at a university is one of the most important in the professional development of a future teacher. Studying at the university is a basis where professionally important skills and personality traits are formed. Furthermore, this is an important period of the adaptation of the novice teacher and his/her consolidation in the profession. There are also, acquisition of professional experience, the development of personal qualities and qualities necessary for the performance of professional activities, the formation of career aspirations, the development of self-development abilities.

We faced problems in the implementation of the “teacher-student-student” model because not all students are ready for pedagogical interaction, for pedagogical cooperation, they do not have the necessary communication skills, and a clear idea about their future profession. Some students have no idea what practical skills modern elementary school teachers should have. Accordingly, these students have not formed professional competencies. Another problem is that experienced teachers working with students and children choose an authoritarian way of pedagogical interaction. Teachers with more work experience with refuse to choose an interactive learning model when you need to be more equal with a student and an elementary school student. And for the implementation of pedagogical interaction, it is necessary for the interlocutors to accept each other as equal partners of this communication, which in practice of the system “teacher – student”, “teacher – student” is quite rare.

To summarize our research, it should be noted that it is not enough for a mentor to be just an experienced, highly qualified teacher, with his/her established system of pedagogical activity. It is necessary to develop your creative potential, constantly be in scientific pedagogical research, improve your forms and methods of work, carry out interpersonal communication with colleagues (learn from others' experiences and share your own developments).

Conclusion

The model of mentoring “teacher-student-student” was created by us in the system of continuous education of Kazan Federal University and it was implemented in children's theater “Rainbow” during the 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 school years. For the effective implementation of the developed teacher-student-student mentoring model, we developed recommendations: 1. The process of teaching in a children's theater according to the “teacher-student-student” model should be a complex unity of the teacher’s activity and the activities of students and pupils and it should be directed towards a common goal - to equip students with knowledge, skills, skills, competencies, to their development and upbringing. Teaching in a children's theater should not only be a process of mastering what is given by a teacher: this is the complex process of cognitive activity. 3. Stand Iku needs to combine rigidity and respect from the teacher to the student. 4. It is necessary to build the ability of all participants of the educational process (teacher-student-student) to dialogical thinking and communication. 5. It is necessary to design the dialogical communication - setting the openness of the positions of its participants .6. Every student and elementary school student should be engaged with the expectation of something interesting, exciting, new, causing him a feeling of "joyful anxiety."

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